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Unseeable Bodies, Forbidden Spaces: Dalit Girlhood, Female Gaze and Cinematic Resistance in the Tamil Film *Maadathy*

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Abstract:

This paper is a feminist, anti-caste analysis of the Tamil film *Maadathy: An Unfair Tale* (2019) directed by Leena Manimekalai. The focus is on how it narrates “Dalit girlhood” through visual strategies that expose and resist caste and gender oppression. Drawing on Dalit feminist thought, intersectionality, feminist film theory, spatial theory and magical realism, the study examines the spatial and bodily regulation of the protagonist *Yosana*, whose life is constrained by “caste-based unseeability” and “moral policing”. Using qualitative interpretative film analysis, critical discourse analysis and feminist visual methodologies, the paper unpacks key cinematic motifs like gaze, silence, emotion and spatial segregation to show how *Maadathy* critiques the social and symbolic erasure of Dalit women. The findings reveal that the film challenges hegemonic visual culture by reclaiming the female gaze, deploying subaltern aesthetics and mobilising magical realism as a mode of resistance. Ultimately, *Maadathy* emerges as a radical anti-caste, feminist cinema that reframes the politics of “seeing” “knowing” and “remembering” from the margins.

Keywords: Dalit feminism, caste, unseeability, female gaze, intersectionality, magical realism, *Maadathy*, subaltern resistance, spatial regulation, feminist cinema.

Introduction

In the broader discourse of Indian cinema, caste remains an underrepresented subject, particularly when intersected with gender and spatial marginalisation. Director Leena Manimekalai's *Maadathy: An Unfairy Tale* (2019), is a critical intervention in a visual landscape by focusing on the lived experiences and tragic death of a Dalit teenage girl from the Puthirai Vannar caste, a community historically labelled “unseeable” and pushed to the social margins of the caste Hindu society. This is the only known film (India and abroad) that has recorded the challenges of a community that is heavily discriminated and considered “unseeable” in the name of caste. The film reclaims not only narrative space but also cinematic visibility for those rendered “invisible” by the dominant social order.

“Unseeability” refers to the deliberate removal of Dalit bodies, especially those of women, both from visual and spatial presence in public life. In India, caste enforces this not only through physical exclusion but also through symbolic erasure of their existence. Within this representation, Dalit girlhood becomes a site of intense regulation. They surveil her body, restrict her movement and deny her subjectivity. Dalit feminist scholars such as Sharmila Rege (2006), Anupama Rao (2003) and S.Paik (2014) have long argued that the experiences of Dalit women cannot be adequately captured by savarna feminists or purely Marxist paradigms. Instead, a distinct Dalit feminist lens is necessary. A perspective that accounts for the intersectional violence of caste, gender, sexuality and labour.

Through the lens of feminist film theory (Mulvey, 1975; de Lauretis, 1987), intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991) and spatial theory (Ahmed, 2006; Lefebvre, 1991), this paper offers a critical analysis of *Maadathy* as a cinematic narrative that resists the hegemonic structures in Tamil cinema. The protagonist *Yosana* is not merely a passive victim of caste-sexual violence, but a symbolic figure, whose journey from girlhood to deification brings forth the mechanisms of moral policing and spatial segregation. Her desire, pain and longing are

rendered visible through deliberate choices in mise-en-scene and narrative temporality. Importantly, the film mobilises magical realism, a narrative technique often employed in subaltern literature (Angulo, 1995) to foreground indigenous epistemologies of resistance.

This study explores how *Maadathy* represents the spatial and bodily regulation of Dalit girlhood through the lens of caste and what this representation reveals about the denial of agency, sexuality and subjecthood in a caste-oppressive society. By engaging with both form and content, the paper situates *Maadathy* as a rare instance of anti-caste feminist cinema that refuses erasure and inscribes subaltern girlhood onto the cinematic canvas with urgency, defiance and profound humanity.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws upon an interdisciplinary set of theoretical frameworks to analyse *Maadathy* as a site where caste, gender, spatiality and visibility intersect. Each framework offers a lens to understand the film's narrative and aesthetic strategies about the systemic marginalisation of Dalit womanhood.

Dalit Feminist Thought

This study uses Dalit feminist thought to assess the experiences of Dalit women, as they are uniquely shaped by caste-based patriarchy that cannot be subsumed within savarna or mainstream feminist frameworks. The works of Sharmila Rege (2006), S.Paik (2014) and Gail Omvedt (1990) explain how the caste system exerts control over Dalit women's labour, sexuality and mobility. Rege's (2006) study emphasizes that caste and gender are co-constitutive. Historically, Dalit women's bodies are exploited both productively and reproductively. This framework foregrounds how the casteist gender violence regulates and

polices *Yosana* and her mother *Veni*'s bodies and how it ultimately sanctifies *Yosana* through deification.

Feminist Film Theory

Under the category of feminist film theories, Laura Mulvey (1975) and Teresa de Lauretis (1987) provide tools for analysing the gaze, visual pleasure and the structuring of desire within cinematic representation. Mulvey's concept of the "male gaze" critiques how mainstream cinema often constructs women as passive objects of visual consumption. In contrast, de Lauretis idea of "technologies of gender", highlights how film forms and narrative position women as both "subject" and "objects" of knowledge and power. This study uses these insights to examine *Maadathy*'s subversion of visual norms through its female-centric gaze, camera work and spectatorship structures.

Intersectionality

Kimberle Crenshaw's (1991) concept of intersectionality is employed to account for the overlapping systems of caste and gender that structure *Yosana*'s lived reality. Intersectionality allows for a nuanced understanding of how caste-based discrimination intensifies gendered violence and vice versa. The film does not portray *Yosana*'s oppression as simply gendered or merely caste-based. However, it shows how these structures coalesce to render her vulnerable, hyper-visible in violation and invisible in life.

Spatial Theory

Henry Lefebvre (1991) and Sara Ahmed (2006) lay the foundations for theorising how societies produce space and orient bodies within it. Lefebvre conceptualises space as both a product and a producer of social relations, while Ahmed (2006) explores how bodies are shaped

through their orientation toward some spaces and away from others. In *Maadathy* space functions not merely as background but as a critical determinant of caste control. The spatial segregation of the people of the Puthirai Vannar caste, their placement in the outskirts and their restricted access to roads, rivers and villages reveal the enforcement of caste boundaries through spatial logic, reinforcing “unseeability”.

Magical Realism and subaltern storytelling

According to Maria Elena Angulo (1995) describes magical realism as a narrative technique frequently used in feminist and subaltern writing to contest dominant epistemologies. This mode merges myth and realism, enabling marginalized communities to reclaim their histories through layered timelines and metaphysical imagery. *Maadathy* draws on this tradition by embedding myth and spiritual impact into its storytelling. The deification of *Yosana* is not just a symbolic compensation for her erasure; it also shows how caste society recognizes Dalit women only posthumously, once sanctified.

Together, these theoretical frameworks offer a multidimensional lens through which we analyse how *Maadathy* constructs resistance, exposes structural violence and reclaims visibility for Dalit girlhood within and beyond the cinematic frame.

Literature Review

In recent years, scholarly interest in caste and gender within Indian visual culture has grown considerably. Yet, “Dalit girlhood” remains underexplored, especially when examined through the medium of cinema. This literature review situates *Maadathy* within the intersections of Dalit feminist thought, feminist film theory, intersectionality and caste based spatial politics. It also engages with recent academic treatments of the film and its contemporaries.

Representations of caste and gender in Tamil cinema

Recent studies on *Maadathy: An Unfairytale* highlight the film's significance in discussions of caste, gender and visual resistance in Indian cinema. Jayakumar (2023) presents a comparative analysis of *Maadathy* and *Lipstick under my Bhurkha*, focusing on how both the films articulate the female gaze within patriarchal cinematic contexts. He contends that *Maadathy* challenges dominant visual norms by portraying *Yosana* not merely as an object of desire but as a subject who desires, thereby highlighting her agency in scenes that Indian cinema has historically denied to Dalit female characters.

Shaji (2020) examines *Maadathy* as a narrative of sexual violence and symbolic silencing, particularly through its portrayal of the Puthirai Vannar caste. This reading resonates with Dalit feminist critiques of the systemic erasure of representation. It underscores how “rape” in the film functions not merely as an act of physical violence but as a deliberate social tool to maintain caste hierarchies and enforce subjugation. This analysis decodes how indigenous and Dalit women's trauma is rendered through cinematic language. Shaji underscores the structural pattern of violence embedded within caste-patriarchal logics.

By contextualizing *Maadathy* within a broader political critique, Mehta and Mini (2025) examine how censorship and Hindutva populism intersect to marginalize Dalit narratives. They argue that the film serves as a counter-hegemonic archive that records subaltern pain, agony and resistance in a political climate hostile to dissent. Their discussion highlights how *Maadathy* not only portrays the lived experiences of caste-oppressed communities but also troubles the aesthetics of visibility and representation politics.

Together, these studies affirm *Maadathy*'s place within anti-caste feminist cinema and establish a foundation for further exploration of its narrative, visual and ideological complexities. This paper specifically focuses on how the film visualizes the spatial and bodily

regulation of Dalit girlhood and on how magical realism and female gaze are mobilised to narrate resistance within oppression.

Recent studies on anti-caste cinema in Tamil acknowledge an anti-caste visual grammar in the works of directors like Pa.Ranjith, Mari Selvaraj, Vetri Maaran, P.Jananathan, Leena Manimekalai and others. Velayutham and Devadas (2021) regard *Maadathy* as a pivotal work in Tamil feminist cinema, highlighting its shift in portraying Dalit subjectivity from being confined to narratives of victimhood to expressing agency through visual style and storytelling. Similarly, Edachira (2020) points to the aesthetic shift toward “anti-caste cinema”, arguing that these films challenge dominant caste representations and also cultivate subaltern spectatorship by employing experimental visual forms.

Suganthi-Singh (2021), in her detailed review of *Maadathy*, coins the term “patria-caste” to describe how the film documents the permissibility of sexual violence against Dalit girls in a dominant caste-driven patriarchal system. *Maadathy* portrays the “geographies of fear” and the violated spatiality endured by Vannar women, framing their bodies as contested sites of caste and gender oppression (Suganthi-Singh, 2021).

Jeeva, Padmanabhan and Sunesh (2025), through a Dravidian ideological lens, examine Karnan (2021) as a powerful cinematic articulation of collective resistance. The study highlighted the film’s visual grammar rooted in rural geographies and mythic symbolism constructing a liberatory aesthetic that changes upper-caste hegemony and affirms Dalit subjectivity.

Manoharan (2020), in his analysis of *Kabali* and *Kaala*, explores how Rajinikanth’s cinematic presence intersects with themes of Dalit assertion and Tamil nationalism. He argues that these films offer a radical departure from caste-neutral narratives by foregrounding urban Dalit masculinities and community organisation, thus embedding anti-caste resistance within the fabric of popular cinema.

Lefebvre's (1991) spatial triad and Sara Ahmed's (2006) work on orientation offer useful conceptual tools to understand the spatial marginalisation depicted in *Maadathy*. The film situates the Puthirai Vannar community at the literal and symbolic margins of the village, highlighting how caste operates spatially to dictate who can be seen, where and by whom. Dhanda and Manoharan (2002) argue that the film's use of space - forests, rivers and the outskirts not only illustrate caste apartheid but also mark a geography of resistance and haunting.

The use of magical realism in *Maadathy* aligns with global subaltern storytelling traditions that collapse myth and reality to render trauma narratable (Angulo, 1995). The film mythically transforms Yosana into a local deity, using this as cultural commentary and as a narrative strategy to critique the posthumous value often attached to Dalit female bodies, a motif that appears across Indian oral traditions and ritual practices.

These works together establish a growing body of scholarship that situates Tamil cinema as a critical site for negotiating caste politics, while also revealing gaps in representation, especially of Dalit girlhood and female subjectivity that *Maadathy* addresses through its feminist anti-caste lens. This study extends these arguments by focusing specifically on how the film visualizes the spatial and bodily regulation of Dalit girlhood and on how magical realism and the female gaze are mobilised to narrate resistance within oppression.

Research Gap

The recent scholarship treated *Maadathy* as a pivotal anti-caste feminist text. But there are significant analytical gaps, particularly regarding the intersection of spatial, bodily and emotional regulation of Dalit girlhood through caste-based "unseeability" and the visual structuring of desire. This paper addresses the gap by combining Dalit feminist theory, spatial analysis and feminist film methodology to foreground how *Maadathy* depicts oppression and

crafts a counter-visual language of resistance, centering the interior lives, desires and agency of Dalit girls.

Methodology

This study employs a qualitative, interpretative methodology grounded in feminist film theory, Dalit feminist thought and critical discourse analysis to examine *Maadathy: An Unfairytale* (2019) as a cinematic site of anti-caste feminist resistance. The film is a rich visual narrative to analyse how caste and gender intersect in the regulation of space, visibility and subjectivity.

Following the protocols established by scholars such as Bordwell and Thompson (2010), this study uses a qualitative interpretative film analysis method to examine the film's mise-en-scene and symbolic imagery to understand how caste, space and gender are rendered and resisted cinematically. To unpack the ideological undercurrents of caste and gender in the film's narrative structure, the study uses Critical discourse analysis (Fairclough, 1995; van Dijk, 1998). CDC is employed to analyse dialogues, silence and narrative absences focusing on how language and storytelling work to either reproduce or resist dominant ideologies. The study integrates feminist visual methodologies (Rose, 2016), particularly drawing from Laura Mulvey's (1975) "male gaze" and Teresa de Lauretis's (1987) "technologies of gender" to analyse how the gaze operates in the film. Additionally, the analysis uses Dalit feminist optics to critique visual regimes that either erase or objectify Dalit women. This dual framework investigates who has the right to look, be looked at or be rendered invisible in the cinematic frame. *Yosana's* moments of desire, punishment and erasure are closely studied to understand the power dynamics embedded in visual and narrative representation.

Key Analytical categories

To structure the analysis, the study applies six interrelated categories such as space, body, gaze, voice or silence, emotion and resistance across the visual, spatial and discursive dimensions of the film. Spatial analysis is used to examine the cinematic encoding of spatial segregation, placement of character in the frame and the visual boundaries that representing caste apartheid.

The analysis tries to find out how the Dalit female body is controlled, exposed, sanctified or erased, who has the power to look, desire or surveil, whether the film inverts or disrupts the patriarchal, casteist gaze, and the use of female gaze in a subaltern context. When, where and to whom do the lower caste people speak and when does the society silence them? How does the film code emotions like fear, longing, shame and joy? Are these emotions punished, repressed or allowed to emerge fully? What visual strategies does the film use to resist casteist narratives? Does the film present counter-gazes or alternative visual grammars? How does the transformation into deity convey both loss and subaltern agency?

Results and Discussion:

This study's interpretative film analysis of *Maadathy* reveals four major thematic categories that articulate the mechanisms of caste-gender violence and resistance: spatial regulation and unseeability, bodily control and sexual policing, the criminalisation of female desire and the use of counter-visual strategies. These findings interpret the film through the intersecting lenses of Dalit feminist theory, spatial analysis and feminist film theory.

Spatial regulation and unseeability

Maadathy visually encodes caste apartheid by situating the *Puthirai Vannar* community at the geographical and symbolic margins of the village. The film portrays a strict spatial logic

in which Dalits are prohibited from entering upper caste spaces and are also denied access to public roads and rivers. They are physically pushed to the margins in both the rural and urban centres (Guru, 2000). They may only cross the river during moments of death emphasizing their existential and spatial liminality.

The film transforms landscape into a metaphor: forests, bushes, barren rocky mountains, caves, shadows, riverbanks and doorless, wall-less huts become “casted spaces” where Dalit bodies may exist only in invisibility. The spatial constraints affirm Gopal Guru’s (2020) idea of “marginalized notion of time”, in which Dalits cannot move freely even within their restricted spaces during the day time, when the upper castes occupy them. Guru explains that the upper castes regulate Dalit movement according to the purity and pollution divide. In one scene, *Veni* and *Yosana* run behind the bushes and hide when an upper caste man approaches on a remote road. He threatens them with abusive language, illustrating not only the “marginalized but stigmatized notion of time” (Guru, 2000) but also the “politics of unseeability”, in which Dalits are essential to the functioning of caste society but must remain invisible to preserve upper caste purity.

Yosana enters the village without anyone noticing and she is confronted by the villagers for entering the space and asking why she came and whether she intended to steal. When she transgresses the traditional boundaries of the village (Guru, 2000), men gang-rape her. In another instance, an upper-caste man forcibly sexually abuses her mother, *Veni*, in the space where she is permitted to live. These incidents reveal how spatial marginality denies the women of the community both protection and autonomy over their own bodies.

Sound, silence and the muted voices of Dalit women

The upper caste men in the film are vocal, violent and entitled to express their desire, assert rights and threaten without restraint. In contrast, the lower caste men are denied even the

basic right to speak and this silencing is intensified in the case of the lower caste women. While the caste-Hindu women also face patriarchal constraints, their position differs significantly from that of Dalit women, whose marginalisation stems from both caste and gender. In the film, *Yosana* speaks audibly only in her intimate conversations with animals and her grandmother. Even during moments of sexual assault, both *Veni* and *Yosana* speak in subdued tones, pleading to be left alone, rather than resisting openly, which renders them almost voiceless.

The comparison between the panchayat leader's invocation of divine festivals that are loud and celebratory, the construction of goddess statue and ritual worship, alongside the dismissal of violence inflicted upon a young girl and the attribution of blame by the caste Hindu women to *Yosana* for "roaming around", as well as the justification of the boys' actions saying, "will the boys keep quiet, when they see girls roaming around like this", "we have given them lives and should we let them talk like this in front of us" and "the temple and its space is defiled by their presence", based solely on their status as a slave caste, illustrate how cultural tradition mystifies caste violence.

The Dalit women speak out only once in the film, after *Yosana's* assault, when they unite to curse the village, voicing their anger against sexual violence and the community's neglect. Thus, the film deploys sound and silence as symbolic markers of the systemic muting of Dalit voices.

Bodily Regulation and Sexual policing

The film narrates caste as embodied in practices like washing menstrual cloths, performing ritualized impure labour and policing sexuality. *Veni* cleans menstrual cloth with visible disgust, cursing the women who send the blood-stained cloth for washing, underscoring the caste logic of "impurity" that marks both the female body and labour. *Yosana's* father does

the laborious work of digging a pit for the dead body and bringing the dirty clothes from the upper caste houses.

Women's bodies, especially are hyper-visible only in moments of violation (Rege, 2006). The community deemed "unseeable" becomes visible only during sexual violence. *Yosana* and *Veni* hide themselves behind bushes whenever upper caste men appear and they walk on the roads only after those men leave. Even then, upper caste men cast furtive glances at them, visually surveying their bodies. The camera describes this status effectively through point-of-view shots that frame the women walking at a distance foregrounded by the upper caste male figures and other elements, thereby depicting the women's marginalized presence in both spatial and visual registers.

The rape of *Yosana* creates a crucial break in the film's visual and narrative flow: it turns her previously "unseeable" body, into a site of heightened visibility while simultaneously removing her agency. This moment reflects what Dalit feminists describe as "spectacularization of caste-sexual violence", a process that objectifies and dehumanizes Dalit women while enabling the upper-caste perpetrators to act with impunity. *Maadathy* powerfully maps the "geographies of fear" and "sacrilege of bodily spaces" that define the lived realities of Vannar women across generations. *Veni's* refers to *Yosana* as "fire in the lap" and *Yosana's* grandfather describes it as the burden experienced by her mother, grandmother and great grandmother. Together, these metaphors articulate the intergenerational trauma of protecting Dalit girlhood within oppressive caste spaces. The film critiques the criminalization of female desire and depicts Dalit women's bodies as sites of both violence and resistance, revealing the emotional and spatial dimensions of caste patriarchy.

Coming of age, desire and caste boundaries

Yosana's journey from girlhood to womanhood is articulated through scenes of desire, longing and erotic gaze, particularly her attraction to *Panneer*. The moment when she observes him bathing naked inverts the male gaze and allows for a Dalit female gaze. It is a radical cinematic gesture rarely permitted in Indian cinema. This visualisation of female desire from a subaltern standpoint is both tender and transgressive. However, this desire is criminalised due to caste. *Yosana's* longing is punished with sexual violence, reaffirming the social prohibition against Dalit women occupying the space of desiring subjects. Thus, her coming of age is not a celebration but a death sentence. This aligns with Paik's (2014) observation that Dalit girlhood is often pathologized and regulated through shame, surveillance and violence. *Yosana's* mother, *Veni*, laments about her daughter: "a beautiful girl born in a slave caste". This statement captures the difficult condition of Dalit girlhood, where to desire is dangerous, to live is dangerous and to grow is sacrilegious. The sexual violations experienced by her and her daughter are not exceptions but "systemic expressions of caste patriarchy". The film also critiques how ritual and religion are mobilised to maintain these structures.

Dalit Feminism, Visual Language and counter gaze

Laura Mulvey's (1975) theory of "male gaze" and Teresa de Lauretis's (1987) idea of "technologies of gender" offer crucial foundations to examine the visual politics of *Maadathy*. *Maadathy* resists dominant cinematic conventions through "magical realism and symbolic imagery". The film's use of visual metaphors like the river and the donkey as silent witnesses, the forest as both a constraint and memory, invokes what Angulo (1995) terms "mythic counter-memory" in feminist resistance literature. These themes construct a visual language that critiques caste structures while affirming the spiritual and affective dimensions of Dalit life.

Yosana is often visually centered in moments of interiority and silence, reclaiming a presence denied in societal discourse. Dalit feminist scholars such as Sharmila Rege (2006), Paik (2014) and Omvedt (1990) have long emphasized that caste shapes Dalit women's sexuality, mobility and labour in ways that mainstream savarna feminism often neglects. Their work highlights that Dalit women are highly visible as labouring bodies yet erased as desiring subjects. These insights have reshaped feminist debates and draw attention to a representational crisis in Indian cinema, where Dalit women's bodies are either ignored or sanctified. This conflict is what *Maadathy* directly confronts by narrating the story of *Yosana*, a Dalit young girl from the Puthirai Vannar community, who is simultaneously “unseeable” and “hyper-visible” at moments of violence.

This work underscores how the film connects bodily violation of *Yosana*, moral policing of the upper caste restricting movement in villages, and disregarding the pain and being brutal to *Yosana* and her family and eventual deification with the same upper caste people visiting the *Maadathy Amman* temple, as a continuum of caste oppression.

Magical realism and deification as acts of resistance

Tamil Cultural historian Tho.Paramasivan (2022), in his Seminal work *Gods and Cultural practices*, emphasizes that any meaningful inquiry into Tamil culture must begin with the study of its deities and ritual traditions. In his ethnographic mapping of divine forms across Tamil Nadu, he identifies a significant category of goddesses such as “Pattini Amman” and “Theeppachiamman”, who are victims of sexual violence and are later deified in the Tamil cultural practice. These deities, often drawn from a historical or folk memory, are worshipped through specific ritual practices that serve both as acts of remembrance and as forms of symbolic restitution.

The figure of *Maadathy Amman*, central to *Maadathy: An Unfairytale*, emerges as a continuation of this cultural practice. Her deification after death situates the narrative within a longstanding Tamil tradition where women subjected to gendered and caste-based violence are transformed into divine figures. Such “ritualistic religions” (Paramasivan, 2022), generally have sacrificial rituals as prayers and the deification could be a way of expressing the community’s collective grief and helplessness, a ritualized acknowledgement of trauma. The act of remembering these women in divine form functions as both a cultural response to injustice and a symbolic preservation of the memory of the violence they endured. *Yosana*’s posthumous deification, her transformation into a local goddess, *Maadathy Amman*, exemplifies what Paik (2014) refers to as symbolic compensation: a substitution of spiritual value for justice, agency and autonomy in subaltern narratives. By transforming *Yosana* into *Maadathy Amman*, the film reconfigures her status from a victim of caste-sexual terror into a goddess of retributive justice, subverting the very system that sought to silence her.

Thus, *Maadathy* not only records a specific instance of caste-gender atrocity but also documents a ritual continuum in Tamil folk religiosity, where the memory of violated female bodies is immortalized through divine representation. In doing so, this highlights the intersection of “gendered suffering”, “caste marginality” and “sacred memorialization”.

By adopting magical realism, *Maadathy* participates in a lineage of “subaltern storytelling” that collapses the boundaries between history, myth, memory and resistance. It visually disorients the viewer from normative time and space, aligning with Lefebvre’s (1991) theory that “space” is ideologically produced. The film’s refusal to offer narrative closure or clear catharsis is itself a political act: it withholds resolution to preserve *Yosana*’s story as a “wound” rather than a “sanitised memory”. The film transforms *Yosana* into *Maadathy Amman*, recasting her from a victim of caste-sexual violence into a goddess of retributive justice, and

in doing so, it subverts the very system that tried to silence her. *Maadathy* transforms trauma into a ‘counter-sacred narrative’.

The film creates a mythical, eerie atmosphere by transforming the male character from the opening scene into a blind figure in a painting, narrating a tale in which all the upper caste villagers lose their sight. It also shows *Yosanas*’s grandfather foreseeing her deification as *Maadathy* before she experiences violence. The elements blend myth and realism. Jacques Derrida’s (1993) concept of “blindness as insight” argues that vision is never complete and that what remains unseen shapes knowledge as much as what we choose to see. *Maadathy* weaponizes this paradox to expose how caste hierarchy operates through enforced blindness: a deliberate refusal to witness oppression. Caste, like other oppressive systems, depends on selective vision: upper castes “do not see” Dalit suffering. When forced to confront it, they dissociate and distance themselves, and mythologise it, engaging in cognitive dissonance. *Maadathy* literalizes this dynamic, with the villagers’ “physical blindness” mirroring their “moral blindness”.

The findings affirm that *Maadathy* is not merely a cinematic narrative but a political intervention into a visual culture of caste and gender. The film challenges the norms that have traditionally rendered Dalit women either invisible or hyper-visible objects of pity, violence or worship. Through its female-authored gaze, *Maadathy* explores the intergenerational trauma of Dalit femininity, the sexual economy of caste and the spatial exclusions that structure everyday violence.

Maadathy, in essence, offers a radical visual grammar of “resistance”, an embodied, gendered and caste-conscious aesthetic that reimagines what it means to see, feel and remember from the margins. It is not merely a film about injustice, but a feminist cinematic method of re-encoding what and who matters in public memory. The use of magical realism and the deification of *Yosana* function not merely as narrative strategies but as acts of “resistance”

rooted in subaltern epistemologies, reclaiming memory and transforming silenced suffering into a form of cultural and political agency.

Conclusion

Maadathy: An Unfairy Tale is a powerful intervention in the landscape of Indian cinema, offering a rare and deeply political portrayal of “Dalit girlhood” through the lens of anti-caste feminism. This study has demonstrated how the film employs spatial and bodily regulation, sexual policing, symbolic deification and magical realism to articulate the interlocking oppressions of caste and gender. It also disrupts dominant visual regimes by mobilising the “female gaze”, affirming subaltern subjectivity and crafting a visual vocabulary of resistance.

The film reveals how caste not only governs who may be seen, heard or desired, but also dictates who is allowed to grow, desire or simply exist with autonomy. Through its portrayal of *Yosana*’s thwarted coming-of-age and her posthumous sanctification, *Maadathy* challenges the viewer to confront how girlhood itself is a denied space for Dalit women. Her deification underscores the tragic reality that recognition often comes only after violence and death, referred to as “symbolic compensation” rather than justice by Dalit feminist scholars like Paik (2014) and Rege (2006).

Nevertheless, *Maadathy* does not leave us only with pain, it offers a cinematic grammar of resistance. Through poetic visuals, subversive framing and mythic realism, it reclaims the act of seeing and being seen from hegemonic frameworks. The film does not merely depict oppression, it demands a “new ethical spectatorship” that acknowledges Dalit women, not as symbols, but as full subjects of history, agency and desire.

The feminist authorship undoubtedly shapes the film’s representation of bodily regulation and sexual policing. Directed by Leena Manimekalai, *Maadathy* adopts a visual

ethic that consciously resists the “spectacularisation” of caste-sexual violence. The film departs from dominant cinematic traditions that objectify the female body or aestheticise trauma, portraying sexual violence without exposing the female body or showing the act explicitly. The film portrays *Yosana*’s rape in darkness, her body completely unseen. At the same time, the male perpetrators are partially visible in their innerwear, an inversion that shifts the visual burden away from the victim. Similarly, *Veni*’s assault is shot from a distance, presenting her body without turning it into a spectacle. Even in the aftermath, as *Veni* walks home in distress, her saree appears dishevelled but never revealing. This visual strategy reframes the Dalit female body not as an object of voyeurism, but as a site of trauma, dignity and resistance. In this context, the female gaze not only critiques the patriarchal and casteist gaze but also enacts a radical refusal to commodify pain, reaffirming the agency of Dalit women even in moments of profound violation.

As a coming-of-age narrative, *Maadathy* reveals that caste is not just a social structure, it is a lived geography of restriction and denial. As an anti-caste feminist film, it calls upon scholars, viewers and filmmakers alike to see, remember and reimagine the *Yosanas* whose stories have long remained in the shadows.

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